
Perceptions and Attitudes Towards Startups of Students in Ahilyanagar District, Maharashtra

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Abstract

This study focused on the perception of the students on entrepreneurship education. Entrepreneurship education is considered as an effective tool for influencing students'. Entrepreneurship education plays an important role in developing perception, "specifically of management students," has become an entrepreneur. An entrepreneurship education should not only provide theoretical knowledge but also able to assist the students on establishing an entrepreneurship mindset through developing entrepreneurial skills, behaviors and attitudes, and train them with entrepreneurial abilities to support them to start their own business venture or engage in entrepreneurship activities. Startups play a crucial role in fostering innovation and economic growth globally. Understanding college students' perceptions and attitudes towards startups is essential for shaping effective entrepreneurship education programs and policies. This paper explores the perceptions and attitudes of college students towards startups, examining their motivations, perceived challenges, and the implications for entrepreneurship education. The study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative interviews and quantitative surveys to gather insights from a diverse sample of undergraduate college students across various disciplines and educational backgrounds in Ahilyanagar District.

Keywords: *Mindset of students, Startups, Entrepreneur, Students, Attitude, Perception.*

Introduction:

It is well known that institutions of higher education, such as colleges and universities, have the responsibility of educating young people to be dynamic change agents in the fields of regional, economic, and social development. The word 'entrepreneur' is derived from the French word 'entreprendre' which means 'to undertake'. "An entrepreneur is one who always searches for change, responds to it, and exploits it as an opportunity. Innovation is the specific tool of entrepreneurs, the means by which they exploit change as an opportunity for a different business or service" - Peter F Drucker.

As per unacademy resources "A startup is a business that is still in its early

phases of development. The startup is established by one or more entrepreneurs to produce services or products for which they consider a scope in the market. Usually, these businesses begin with increased prices and limited revenue; that's why they look for funding from several sources, counting venture capitalists. A startup is a business that aims to grow and expand swiftly, sometimes to dizzying heights. This is one of the characteristics that distinguishes a small business startup. While every startup's path is unique, most firms can go through the same stages as they grow and evolve, referred to as the five stages of startup operations. One can anticipate what each step will bring and adjust their preparations accordingly. Additionally, in order for entrepreneurial

education to be long-lasting, it needs to promote more extensive study and thoughtful analysis applied to real-world situations. All business courses that instruct students to maintain a condition of balance in the global marketplace must emphasize students' commitment as global citizens.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study the perception students interested and reason for choosing an entrepreneurs as a career.
2. To identify different type of perceived barriers faced by the students in the selection of entrepreneurship as a career.
3. To determine the factors influencing students' motivations to join startups or pursue entrepreneurial ventures
4. To investigate college students' attitudes towards entrepreneurship and their inclination towards starting or working for startups in Ahilyanagar District, Maharashtra

Students' Perceptions of Startups:

1. **Job Creation:** Startups are significant contributors to job creation. Studying students' perceptions can help predict future trends in employment preferences and inform workforce development strategies.
2. **Innovation Dynamics:** Startups drive innovation. Understanding how students perceive startups can shed light on potential future trends in innovation and entrepreneurship, influencing policy and investment decisions.
3. **Skills and Knowledge:** Insight into students' perceptions can inform entrepreneurship education programs, ensuring they equip students with relevant skills and knowledge needed to thrive in startup environments.
4. **Entrepreneurial Ambitions:** By studying perceptions, researchers can gauge students' interest in

entrepreneurship and their intentions to start their own ventures. This data is crucial for fostering an entrepreneurial ecosystem.

5. **Curriculum Design:** Insights into students' perceptions can inform the design of entrepreneurship education curricula, ensuring they meet the needs and expectations of future entrepreneurs.
6. **Policy Formulation:** Policymakers can use data on students' perceptions to formulate policies that support entrepreneurship, address barriers, and create conducive environments for startup success.
7. **Social Impact:** Many startups focus on social and environmental impact. Understanding students' perceptions can highlight potential areas for social innovation and sustainable development.
8. **Comparative Studies:** Comparative studies across regions or demographic groups can provide nuanced insights into variations in perceptions and their underlying factors.
9. **Career Aspirations:** Understanding how college students perceive startups can help identify their career aspirations and preferences. This knowledge is essential for startups in attracting and retaining young talent.
10. **Economic Growth:** Startups play a vital role in economic growth. Analyzing perceptions can provide insights into the potential impact of startups on local and national economies.

Statement of the Problem:

In recent years, the landscape of entrepreneurship has evolved significantly, with startups emerging as pivotal drivers of innovation and economic growth. Understanding college students' attitudes towards startups is crucial for several reasons. First, it provides insights into the

factors influencing their career aspirations and decisions regarding employment in innovative, fast-growing enterprises. Second, it sheds light on how educational institutions can better prepare students for the dynamic and often unpredictable startup environment. Third, it offers valuable perspectives for policymakers aiming to foster entrepreneurial ecosystems that attract and retain young talent. So this research paper aims at understanding the attitude and perceptions of college students' towards startups.

Methodology:

This study is based on both primary and secondary data. Simple random sampling method was administered for selecting the sample. The population of the study included 120 undergraduate students. The primary data was collected by questionnaire method. There were questions consisting of demographic factor and perception towards new venture creation intentions and entrepreneur's image. The secondary data was collected from books, reports and online resources. Simple random sampling was chosen and randomly 12 students were selected. The prior confirmation was taken from the respondents. Based on consent distributed and requested for participation in the study. Participants were assured confidentiality and anonymity of the data. Both male and female students participated in the study

Review of Literature:

Arthur, K., & Arthur, A.2 (2020) studied the motivations, entrepreneurial challenges and engagements of 20 graduates of visual arts academic programs in Ghana in the study titled 'The Student Entrepreneurial Journey: Motivations, Entrepreneurial Engagements and Challenges among Recent Graduates of Visual Arts Academic Programs in Ghana'.

The results of the study showed that the students focused on opportunities within their field of specialization using skills acquired as a part of their education as a means of survival. This resulted in the students facing financial, operational, marketing and managerial difficulties. Further research can be carried out to develop better curriculum that teaches students to be growth oriented as well as use their craft towards entrepreneurship

The study conducted by Dr. Mohsin Shaikh found the educational background of the students influence the intention of students to become an entrepreneur. He also recognizes age, autonomy, independence, self-efficiency and ownership have a greater influence on the intention to start venture. Another finding is that the likelihood of venturing into entrepreneurship decrease while the level of education increases

Vivek Raj S N, Murugan V G This article discusses the perception and attitude of college students towards entrepreneurship, student's opinion about barriers of entrepreneurship and factors affecting career choices. A total of 287 students from Chittoor district, Andhra Pradesh, India participated in the survey about the general perception towards entrepreneurship as a career. The Study revealed that majority of the students have positive attitude towards entrepreneurship, and consider lack of awareness as a major hurdle in choosing entrepreneurship as a career and among the factors affecting career choice, interest of the candidates is found to be the most crucial factor. Lack of awareness was identified as a major hindrance to entrepreneurship, and pre-existing inspiration about successful entrepreneurs was found to be strongly associated with the intent to start a new business (Maxwell Ayodele Olokundun, 2017). The study suggests that collaboration between the government and educational institutions to provide more professional courses in

entrepreneurship could act as a catalyst for promoting entrepreneurship. A study by Basu (2014) attempted to develop a working framework for an entrepreneurship education ecosystem in India, with preliminary inputs and evidence. The study proposes future research ideas to facilitate the adoption and further development of the framework, which will aid policymakers of a developing nation.

Limitations of the Study:

The sample size was only around 120 students from only one district, which may not be adequate or appropriate for the entire population and the current situation

may have affected the routine work of the respondents. There is significant future scope for exploring the perceptions of university students on entrepreneurship education. Conducting longitudinal studies to track the perceptions of university students on entrepreneurship education over an extended period. This will help to identify changes in attitudes and perceptions over time. Comparing the perceptions of university students on entrepreneurship education across different universities, courses, and disciplines. This will help to identify the factors that influence student perceptions and how they vary across different contexts.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table: 1 Demographic Factors

Demographic Variable	No. of Respondents	Percentage	
Gender	Male	66	55
	Female	54	45
Parent's Own business	Yes	31	25.83
	No	89	74.16
Parents Monthly Income	< 10,000 per month	20	16.66
	10,000- 25,000 month	45	37.5
	25000 - 50,000 month	46	38.33
	Above 50,000 month	9	7.5

Source: Primary Data

Out of 120 respondents, 55 percentage are male and 45 percentage are female respondents, 25.83 percentage of the respondents' parents have their own business whereas 74.16 percentage of the respondents' parents are not involved in any entrepreneurial activity, 16.66 percentage of

the respondents' parents have per month income below Rs.10,000, 37.5 percentage have income between Rs.10,000 to Rs.25,000, 38.33 percentage have income between Rs.25000 to Rs.50,000 and 7.5 percentage have income above Rs.50,000.

Table: 2 Students' Perception towards startups in Ahilynagar District

Sl. No	Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
1.	It gives freedom to pursue own vision	72	19	14	15	0	120
2.	It gives more flexibility in personal and family life	57	30	19	14	0	120
3.	Entrepreneurs are almost always inventors	63	27	8	8	14	120
4.	It helps to become a business leader	52	23	12	24	09	120
5.	Helpful to give social contribution.	41	21	2	42	14	120
6.	Entrepreneurship is a good way to make lots of money.	11	6	41	43	19	120
7.	It gives potential for career growth and learning.	72	23	6	19	0	120
8.	Entrepreneurship is an honorable profession	63	26	14	6	11	120
9.	Colleges should encourage students to consider entrepreneurship	89	18	13	0	0	120
10.	It gives opportunity for innovation and creativity	58	32	14	9	7	120

Source: Primary data

The above table depicts that 72 percentage of the respondents strongly agree that it gives freedom to pursue own vision, 57 percentage agree that it gives more flexibility in personal and family life. 63 percentage are of the view that entrepreneurs are almost always inventors, 52 percentage believes that it helps to become a business leader, 41 percentage agree that it is helpful to give social contribution, 62 percentage are of the view that it gives potential for career growth and learning, 63 percentage agree that entrepreneurship is an honorable profession, 89 percentage agree that colleges should encourage students to consider entrepreneurship, 58 percentage agree that it gives opportunity for innovation and creativity and only 7 percentage agrees that entrepreneurship is a good way to make lots of money.

Implications of the Study:

Universities should develop an entrepreneurship education curriculum that focuses on equipping students with practical skills and knowledge that they can apply in the real world. Universities should collaborate with industry leaders to develop entrepreneurship education programs that are relevant to the needs of the industry. In This study is important to policy makers and stakeholders in India regarding the design of an entrepreneurship curriculum that can enhance the development of viable business ideas by students of universities. The result of this study will may help for managements of universities on the formulation and implementation of policies, reliable in innovative activities and entrepreneurship education development of undergraduate's programme in the universities.. The findings of this study will guide the development of entrepreneurial skills and aptitudes in

university students, which in turn will motivate the tendency for job creation and reduction in graduate unemployment. There should be regular monitoring and evaluation of entrepreneurship education programs to determine their effectiveness in equipping students with the skills and knowledge needed to succeed in the business world. This research will contribute to existing knowledge in literature of entrepreneurship education and Skill, by developing an intention that will be useful for researchers in further research on related areas of study.

Conclusion:

In summary, startups are pivotal in driving innovation across various sectors, creating jobs, stimulating economic growth, fostering competition, and contributing to societal and environmental progress. Supporting startups through policies, investment, and ecosystem development is essential for nurturing a vibrant entrepreneurial landscape that benefits economies and societies globally. To conclude, studying college students' perceptions of startups is essential for preparing the future workforce, fostering innovation, promoting economic development, shaping educational programs, informing policy decisions, understanding cultural shifts, and contributing to academic research. This research helps build a robust foundation for supporting and advancing the role of startups in society. evaluate the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education in developing students' entrepreneurial skills, knowledge, and attitudes. Overall, this study provides valuable insights into the perceptions of university students on entrepreneurship education and highlights the

need for continuous improvement in the design and delivery of entrepreneurship courses.

References:

1. Athulya (2017). A study on Attitude of commerce students towards entrepreneurship with special reference to Calicut district, Kerala, A journal of Nehru arts and Science College, 5(1), 58-62.
2. Ezekiel Obembe, OluyinkaOtesile, IdyUkpong 2014, Understanding the students' perspectives towards entrepreneurship, Social and Behavioral science. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.06.005.
3. Dr. Suhas B. Diwate 2015, A Study on "The Perception of Management Students towards Entrepreneurship as a Career and Role of Education" International Journal of Advance Research in Computer Science and Management Studies ISSN: 2321-7782 (Online) pp.50 – 54.
4. Gomathi Agathursamy (2023), A Study on Impact of New Start-ups among College Students, Rural Women Empowerment through Entrepreneurship – vol 2, p 245 – 248.
5. Dr. Mohsin Shaikh (2012), STUDENTS INTENTION TOWARDS ENTREPRENEURSHIP: A REVIEW OF EMPIRICAL STUDIES ZENITH International Journal of Business Economics & Management Research Vol.2 Issue 3, March 2012, ISSN 2249 8826 p. 165 – 168.
6. Online resources